

Diazo Coupling of Metal Chelates of Thenoyltrifluoroacetone

K. KRISHNANKUTTY* and JOHNS MICHEAL

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Kerala-673 635

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Aryldiazonium ion is a dominant electrophile and the diazo coupling reaction has been recognised as an electrophilic substitution reaction¹. Metal-1,3-diketones are known to undergo many electrophilic substitution reactions typical of aromatic compounds in view of the quasi-aromatic C_3O_2M ring system present in these compounds^{2,3}. We have reported earlier the substitution of phenyldiazonium ion on metal-acetylacetonates⁴. This communication presents the result of the reaction of phenyldiazonium ion on metal chelates of thenoyltrifluoroacetone (Htta).

Results and Discussion

The composition, melting point and ir spectra of the diazo coupled product of $Cu(tta)_2$ and $Ni(tta)_2$ are identical to that of the intra-molecularly hydrogen-bonded phenylhydrazonothenoxytrifluoroacetone (Hptta)⁵. Thus the ir spectra of the reaction products (sl. nos. 1 and 2 in Table 1) show two strong bands at 1705 and 1640 cm^{-1} due to free trifluoroacetyl carbonyl and hydrogen-bonded

thenoyl carbonyl respectively. The nature and position of all other bands agree well with the spectrum of Hptta. Thus, it appears that these chelates undergo dissociation under the reaction condition and the Htta formed couples with phenyldiazonium ion to form the phenylhydrazone derivative.

Elemental analysis data indicate that phenylazo substitution has occurred only on one of the chelate rings of $Cr(tta)_3$ and $Al(tta)_3$, and on both the chelate rings of $Pd(tta)_2$. This was further confirmed by the reductive cleavage of the azo function using zinc and acetic acid, and the aniline formed was extracted with ether and estimated⁶.

A comparison of the ir spectra of $Cr(tta)_3$, $Al(tta)_3$ and $Pd(tta)_2$ with those of the diazo coupled products show that the C_3O_2M ring system of the former compounds remain almost unaffected in the reaction products. Thus, the ir spectra of the diazo coupled products (sl. nos. 3–5 in Table 1) are characterised by the absence of absorption in the region 1620–1750 cm^{-1} (indicating that both the carbonyl groups are engaged in bonding with metal ion), and the presence of two strong bands at ~ 1605 and ~ 1590 cm^{-1} due to stretching of metal-bonded carbonyl and $C=C$ respectively, as in metal-thenoxytrifluoroacetones^{3,7}. A weak band appearing at 1440 ± 5 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all the three compounds is assignable⁴ to ν_{N-N} . The intensity of the C–H (chelate ring) in-plane bending modes of $Cr(tta)_3$ and $Al(tta)_3$ observed⁷ at $\sim 1140s$ and $\sim 1090w$ cm^{-1} , decreased considerably in the diazo coupled products (sl. nos. 4 and 5) indicating partial substitution. The corresponding bands of $Pd(tta)_2$ at 1148s and 1085w cm^{-1} disappeared in the reaction product (sl. no. 3). Characteristic ν_{M-O} bands of metal thenoyltrifluoroacetones⁷ ($300-470$ cm^{-1}) remain almost unaffected in the spectra of the reaction products.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF REACTION PRODUCTS

Sl. no.	Reaction product of	M.p (°C)/ (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)*		
			C	H	N
1.	$Cu(tta)_2$	122 (Yellow)	50.80 (51.37)	2.28 (2.76)	8.10 (8.59)
2.	$Ni(tta)_2$	122 (Yellow)	50.81 (51.37)	2.28 (2.76)	8.15 (8.59)
3.	$Pd(tta)_2$	185 (Brown)	44.03 (44.42)	2.46 (2.38)	7.67 (7.40)
4.	$Cr(tta)_3$	135 (Green yellow)	43.52 (43.96)	2.21 (2.32)	3.34 (3.42)
5.	$Al(tta)_3$	162 (Red)	45.08 (45.34)	2.18 (2.19)	3.39 (3.53)

*Given in parenthesis are calculated value of Hptta in the case of reaction products 1 and 2, disubstituted product in the case of 3 and monosubstituted products in the case of 4 and 5.

That substitution has occurred on both the chelate rings of $\text{Pd}(\text{tta})_2$, is evident from the ^1H nmr spectrum of the diazo coupled product. The methine proton signal of $\text{Pd}(\text{tta})_2$ at δ 6.25 is absent in the reaction product. The integrated intensities of the aryl proton signals (δ 6.8–7.5) also agree well with the structure 1. The ^1H nmr spectrum of the substitution product of $\text{Al}(\text{tta})_3$ shows a two-proton signal at δ 6.30. This together with the integrated intensities of the phenyl and thienyl proton signals conform to the mono-substituted nature of the product.

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It has been reported³ that electrophilic substitution at the central carbon of metal 1,3-diketonates are very slow when flanked by aryl group at C-1 and a CF_3 group at C-3. This is also true for aryldiazonium ion coupling of 1,3-diketones and metal-1,3-diketonates. Thus, metal-acetylacetonates readily undergo diazo coupling reaction to form arylazo/arylhydrazono substituted derivatives⁴. Whereas in metal thenoyltrifluoroacetates, it appears that only partial substitution is possible even for the more stable $\text{Cr}(\text{tta})_3$ and complete substitution is achieved only in the case of $\text{Pd}(\text{tta})_2$.

Experimental

Copper(II), nickel(II), palladium(II), chromium(III) and aluminium(III) chelates of Htta were

prepared and purified by reported methods³. Phenyl diazonium chloride was obtained through the diazotisation of aniline using sodium nitrite in HCl. Excess nitrous acid present in the diazonium salt solution was destroyed by adding urea. The coupling reaction was carried out as follows.

To a solution of the metal chelate (1 mmol) in methanol, kept cold below 5° was added slowly with stirring a cold aqueous solution of the diazonium salt (2 mmol in the case of bis-chelates and 3 mmol in the case tris-chelates). Sodium acetate was added to maintain the pH of the mixture between 6 and 7. After stirring for about 1 h, the mixture was allowed to attain room temperature slowly. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from hot benzene. Ir spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu model IR 435 spectrometer and nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian XL-100 FT NMR instrument.

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